

ESSENCE AND FEATURES OF UNDERSTANDING NATIONAL IDENTITY IN YOUTH EDUCATION

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Abstract. The article substantiates the essence of awareness of national identity in the education of youth. Education and potential of youth is a very important objective pattern of development and improvement of our country. Now the main goal of every citizen of the country, especially our citizens working in the field of social sciences, is to educate our selfless citizens who love this country, this country, serve the development of the country, and respect its material values. and spiritual values and who promotes them in a certain sense. Circulation is a very important issue.

Keywords: youth, national identity, social sciences, development, physical capabilities, youth education, worldview.

In all eras, teachers have strived to shape the morals and morals of youth, faith and conscience, knowledge and skills of youth in harmony with the requirements and needs of the time. Accordingly, any educational process is ultimately an ideological education in its purpose and essence.

Healthy ideological education also means instilling a high worldview and faith. At the same time, we should not forget that in this matter education, the personal qualities of the teacher and dedication to their work are extremely important. Ghazali writes about this. "The key to educating a murid sheikh (educator) is the same as that of a farmer who clears his surroundings of weeds and thorns so that the blessing growing from the ground brings a good harvest" [3, p.18].

Drawing a conclusion from these thoughts, we should all feel responsible for the education of young people and together fight against evil that is not inherent in our society. After all, the ideal generation and patriotic and highly moral youth are the real successors of our today and tomorrow.

It is known that educational influence, taking into account the characteristics of each age period, forms a person's self-awareness. The sooner a person's sense of self-awareness awakens, the faster a personal point of view, self-esteem, and assessment of one's practical and physical capabilities appear. National identity and national spirit are interconnected and based on each other. Through awareness of national identity, a nation comes to appreciate its history. The formation and development of the worldview, education, knowledge and

thinking of young people is an urgent task of today. “The education of the younger generation,” said the head of state, “has always been important and relevant.” But in the 21st century in which we live, this question really becomes a matter of life and death” [1, p. 504-505]. Because “in the modern world, merciless competition, contradictions and conflicts are becoming increasingly acute” [2].

Youth are our future, the decisive force of our tomorrow. The reforms being implemented in our country are based on the noble goal of caring for the young generation, which is physically healthy, mentally mature, has modern knowledge and skills, is capable of independent and creative thinking, and has high intellectual potential.

Indeed, among the goals of democratization of our society and the formation of civil society, the problem of youth, which is the basis and support for the development of our country, is among the priority issues of a person and his interests.

We will mobilize all the forces and capabilities of our state and society so that our youth have high intellectual and spiritual potential, think independently, become people equal to their peers in any field, and become happy” [2].

In today's age of advanced information and communication technology, some people use these technologies for creativity, science and development to achieve their goals. In particular, the Odnoklassniki website alone is visited by about two million people from our country. Most of them are young people. It will not be an exaggeration to say that the main goal of such networks is to capture the minds and hearts of our students, influence the minds and emotions of a nation or people of a certain country or region, subordinate them to their worldview, make them morally weak and subordinate. As a result, it becomes a habit among young people to spend time playing computer games rather than reading books and watching films of different genres with superficial content.

The rapidly changing reality requires the search for new and more effective ways to protect the consciousness and worldview of young people. To develop a healthy spiritual need in our youth, we must give them sufficient knowledge and understanding of our spiritual and cultural history. Today in our country, in particular in educational institutions, large-scale work is being carried out to raise the morale of young people, strengthen the sense of national identity and its widespread propaganda. In this regard, students are provided with a wide range of knowledge and understanding through subjects such as history,

etiquette and basic spirituality. A person learns a lot from life. In particular, life teaches us many lessons in terms of manners, spirituality and understanding of national identity. In our time, the more people and representatives of a nation deeply and comprehensively know their history, morals, sciences through the realization of national identity, the more they become participants in the events of modern history and on this basis highly value the achievements of their people in the past and mourn their defeats. The feelings, thoughts and aspirations of our compatriots of the past begin to penetrate the feelings, minds and hearts of our contemporaries who have reached such a state.

Many of our philosophers, political scientists and educators have given several definitions to the concept of national identity, based on scientific research. In particular, Professor S. Otamurodov considered the realization of national identity an important sign of a nation and put forward the idea that a nation that does not realize itself cannot rise to the level of a full-fledged nation [4, p. 21-22]. J. Bahranov defined it as follows based on a study of issues of understanding a person's national identity. "Understanding a person's national identity means, first of all, knowledge of belonging to a certain nation (ethnic group), knowledge of the historical place of this nation in development, loyalty to national characteristics, understanding of the needs and interests of one's nation. (ethnic group) today, knowing the paths of its future development, and conscientiously serving for this purpose. It is meant to be done" [3, p. 39].

According to V. Kh. Kochkarov, "understanding national identity is the perception of the national and representative place of each nation in the general cultural base of language, culture, historical heritage, spirituality, customs and traditions."

[6, p. 12]. Russian scientists also study the concept, meaning and features of the development of national identity. For example, E. A. Yablokova writes: "Awareness of national identity is people's understanding of their belonging to a particular nation, the place of the state in the system of internal, interethnic, interstate public relations" [7, p. 105].

Education is mainly carried out in the family, society and educational institutions. Under the influence of established relationships in the family, high human qualities are formed from early childhood, such as loyalty to one's duty, patriotism, determination, and understanding of human dignity. As a result of the influence of sincerity, reasonable relationships, and a warm psychological atmosphere in marriage, family members develop humility, sincerity, courtesy, kindness, kindness, patience, correctness, gentleness, cordiality, kindness,

exactingness, conscientiousness, responsibility, and accuracy. and self-respect based on moral education. If family relationships are built on the basis of rudeness and indifference, then in the spiritual world of family members such vices as pessimism, stubbornness and obstinacy are formed. This indicates that moral and legal education in the family is not carried out properly [8, p. 157-159].

Also, in the system of social studies among students, it is necessary to pay attention to current methodological issues of understanding the national identity of young people:

- the theoretical significance of the study of the epistemological features of the life-strategic understanding of youth allows us to realize scientific fantasies (later);

- the concept that the functional construction of national identity is a determining factor in human social behavior;

- working characteristics of national identity - accepting the imagination of the nation as one's own, understanding its belonging to an ethnic society, giving significance to the country through religious unity, language and traditions, values and respect for other social groups;

- responsibility and accountability are one of the active activities of humanity, and human participation in choosing a life path is a life strategy;

- concepts about pedagogical paths, forms and methods that form a socially active life position in students.

The theoretical significance of this work lies in the fact that the identified identities not only reveal the features of national identity, but also identify and study a number of patterns in the formation of national identity in accordance with the requirements of the ideology of our republic and universal human values. Also, language is of paramount importance at the first stage of the formation of national identity. It is known that language is one of the main components of national identity. Because the language is understood as a native language, and representatives of this nation speak this language to each other. Through the national language, mutual understanding between representatives of their people, national and cultural information, information, and cultural heritage are transmitted from generation to generation.

The second stage of realization of national identity covers the periods of adolescence and youth. The uniqueness of these youthful periods, a conscious attitude towards one's nation, and the formation of national identity depend on many factors. Young people are very interested in the spiritual culture of their

own and other peoples. At this stage, a system of ideas and assessments about the national identity of one's own people is formed in comparison with representatives of other peoples. A sense of national pride and pride in the spiritual heritage of one's people also develops.

Conclusion. Based on the above considerations, the following conclusion can be drawn:

- creation of differentiated programs in educational institutions that will help to understand the continuity of education of national moral qualities in accordance with the age of students;
- effective use of resources that reflect national moral qualities, values, and heritage of our ancestors in textbooks and educational materials;
- raising spiritual and moral education in educational institutions to the level of today's requirements, organizing various cultural, political, social events that influence the worldview of young people;
- deepen the spiritual and moral knowledge of teachers, use historical sources that form national pride when conveying the secrets of their science to young people;
- holding round tables and meetings of young people with leading, exemplary, heroes of our time in various fields;
- it is very important to visit holy places, organize trips to historical places, and get acquainted with folklore in the formation of the national identity of young people.

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